

Analysis of Performance Appraisal System to Evaluate the High Productivity of Employee: A Case Study on Bengal Group of Industries in Bangladesh

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Effective management and evaluation are essential for employees in an organization. A performance appraisal system needs to achieve the desired productivity of employee. Although a variety of factors are considered to support the performance appraisal system that impacts performance within the organization. Appropriate performance appraisals and appropriate influences from management for promotion will not delay employee productivity. Moreover, performance assessment is about the ability of an organization to develop its employees. On the other hand, communication plays an important role in multistage process of performance appraisal. However, recording additional information about staff assessment results, analysis and reporting is a process of performance appraisal in their work environment.

In addition, performance appraisal; terms of examination and evaluation are often used in human resource management in most businesses. Also, Performance appraisals determine who needs to train and who should be promoted or fired. The organization uses management by objective as an essential method to achieve the goals and achieve the desired strategies and performance enhancements and capabilities. This case study follows a comprehensive critique of the current effective identification and performance appraisal system. The results of the analysis included in this study highlight the positive contribution of performance appraisal system to employee productivity.

However, there are some practical recommendations to the management of Bengal Group for continuous improvement and gain the benefits from performance appraisal.

Keywords: PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL SYSTEM, EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVIT.

Introduction

Performance appraisal systems are important for analyzing employee performance in an organization. The

organization can move forward to achieve the goals and targets by employees through using a performance appraisal system. The most important tool that the organization considers is the performance appraisal system, to create information that gives determination about various aspects of personnel such as promotions and services that are really useful. Performance appraisal systems assess employees' contribution through appraisal and employees performance to organizational targets (Craig, S. E. et., Al., 1986). If performance is related to the gathering of information and making decisions, and provide the basis for assessing the usefulness of personnel divisions such as promotion, selection, training and compensation to achieve organizational goals. Adequate performance appraisal system infrastructure can help employees clearly understand their roles and responsibilities in relation to the organization's targets as well as to evaluate their performance. The management can determine by the system about how well the employees are performing at their tasks, communications and making plans to improve their performance. However, the process for evaluating employees performing on their assigned tasks is quite satisfying. A performance appraisal system is a procedure for creating an environment in which employees are qualified to perform their best (Pravin Worker and Kishor Wararkar, 2016).

Materials and methods

A Practical Observation of Bengal Group of Industries

The Bengal Group is a well-known, organized and leading business center that contributes to the economic development of Bangladesh. Bengal Group began its journey in 1969 in Dhaka, Bangladesh with more than 9,000 employees. The Bengal Group operates and shares an extraordinary commitment to excellence in Bangladesh. Bengal Group has a wide range of activities in the fields of plastics, adhesives, metals, paper, real estate, agriculture, food, banking, insurance, electronic media and energy.

In 1971, after the independence of Bangladesh, the Bengal Group introduced a performance appraisal system in the organization, one of the main goals of which is employee productivity to support the work of managers to develop the goal of the organization. The performance appraisal system is a process of connecting employees with the goals of the organization and improving employee performance. The performance appraisal analysis focuses on employee work and measurement plans and the process of communicating with employees and superiors. This system helps to define expectations that employees and managers will prepare a work and development plan from the end of the year.

However, Bengal Group uses management by objectives (MBO) method for evaluating the employee performance. The employee appraisal system takes into account the achievement of the goal set by agreement between employees and managers. This type of work should be prepared for collaboration between managers and employees (Gail Warren 2013, 76). While the main dimensions of all works are the quality, quantity, cost and timing of serving and it can be expressed differently in different positions. The Bengal group held two documentary six-month feedback sessions to ensure all employees receive feedback to increase their productivity.

This case study in the Bengal group examined the strength and weakness that need to improve by performance appraisal system. Although a small number of respondents may not be included in the entire study, this analysis should be of interest to those managers who want to think critically and look for ways to improve the performance appraisal system in their organization.

Figure: HRM department of Bengal Group of Industries

Literature Review

The performance appraisal system is the most inevitable element of successful implementation of business and human resources policies (Kressler, 2003). In addition, the promotion and rewarding to staff through the performance appraisal system that reveals the effectiveness and efficiency of the organizational development programme for staff (Pulakos, 2003). A precise way of conducting the performance appraisal system in the organization is required in order to gain access to the abilities and productivity of staff. While assessing the

productivity of employees is a difficult task for the management of the organization, it is seen as a parameter of organizational judgements (Folger et al., 1992). Management forms emphasized goals that contain consistent employee values.

A performance appraisal system is based on work-related accountability that provides unique performance measures and combines different weighting schemes with adjustments to employee attitudes and actions, such as emotional commitment (Morrow, 2011). According to Stefan and Dorfman (1989), the success of the performance appraisal method depends on the performance of the employee and on how the performance of the task provides an obvious opportunity for remuneration. Dobbins, Cardi and Platz-Vieno (1990), presented five results using ratings as baseline data to increase productivity, reduce staff turnover, improve morale, and have a sense of fairness among staff, link productivity and Incentives.

Employee productivity is an important part of a business that involves people, directing and channeling (Steers and Porter 1987). Herzberg (1987), argues that in order to increase labor, it is necessary to use a variety of evaluations to pay and perceived by the appraisal system at work. Also, the extrinsic incentives can boost the employee productivity without any doubt. Hamner (1987), stated that performance appraisal system can run for a variety of reasons if incentives are not relevant to the results, appraisal and awards are not viewed as compensation, and distrust and honesty about the merit. Although, some merit pay scheme may encourage the non-quality work practices because an individual employee attempts most of the time to make personal gains and disservice of the whole organization (Hickey and Ichter, 1997).

However, employees need a special evaluation system or various methods of measuring employee performance. But, employees' performance is related to the strengths or limitations of belief, and in particular, management is able to receive a positive response from the employees regarding productivity by applying the performance appraisal system.

Methodology

The study is organized as a case study and camps for 70 employees, including 38 middle managers and 12 senior employees. The techniques are used to classify and select up to 50 employees in tiered easy to use manner. The questionnaires and key correspondence interview was processed for primary data collection. Secondary data were obtained from the human resources department of the Bengal Industries Group. The survey found that some of the respondents' personal feelings were not hidden where the information assortment is a serious problem because it almost damages employees' personal lives, moral contemplation and manner. (Mugenda and Mugenda 2003). The author noted that respondents were aware of the systematic use of the information and obtained it and did not disclose or discuss it with unauthorized persons. However, measures were taken to protect respondents from psychological harm during data collection. The speed was found to be higher to avoid interruptions to the respondents. The author has the ability to select the result to view the final tool and collect data for the study. The collected data is modified, encoded and processed using an Excel spreadsheet.

Analysis the Impact of Performance Appraisal System in Bengal Group of Industries

Employee's perception to the performance appraisal system reveals the satisfactory level of employee achievement and determines the degree to which positive increases in employee productivity and organizational performance (Culbertson, Henning and Payne, 2013). However, employees performance of the current performance appraisal system followed by Bengal Group in terms of employee productivity and organizational performance, is based on the satisfactory level of performance of current performance appraisal that staff as reflected in the following figure: 5.1

Figure: 5.1: Employees impression on current performance appraisal system.

More than 74% of the figure above is happy with the current performance rating system, and 26% have expressed little concern about their current performance rating. Notwithstanding, these findings facilitate further research into these concerns or biases. Although, workplace conducting can be found between perception of employees and managers, and a strict perspective is absolutely necessary for effective use of performance appraisal. Also, personal perception from the participants further asked to express regarding the performance appraisal of Bengal Group for organization development and employees productivity.

On the other hand, identify individual strengths and weaknesses on their productivity by contributing to performance evaluation that providing an opportunity to customize professional plans. From the analysis of research questions "Does the performance appraisal system lead to employee's productivity?" the result overall 92% of all participants are agreed that performance appraisal system leads to improve staffs, support, vision, and organization performance which is based on skill and employee productivity. In Figure 5.2 below, acceptance of employee productivity has been demonstrated through a performance appraisal system, and this process also contributes to the achievement of organizational goals.

Figure: 5.2: Do performance appraisal system leads to employee's productivity?

Furthermore, this analysis represents the majority of the workforce, 52 % fully agreed that employee's productivity can only increase by using the performance appraisal system. The implications of the performance appraisal system are derived from its impact on employees' skills and competencies, which, in turn, makes the employees' productivity in a way that is similar to the performance of an organization. The satisfactory level of performance appraisal system currently in use at Bengal Group is very high.

However, 8 % of participants do not agree with the current performance appraisal system and urgently need appropriate coordination to develop the performance appraisal concept. Also, refer to those who see dissatisfaction with what is expected of them and who need to regularly comply with personal performance appraisal that can be expected to contribute performance appraisal system towards employee productivity.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The main purpose of the performance appraisal system is to evaluate the productivity and performance of the organization. This case study shows that Bengal Group has a deeper understanding of employee productivity and benefits. This study establishes a link between employees' improvement and organizational benefits. The performance appraisal system improves the pros and cons of an employee's job performance. However, human resource management literature exists towards employee's motivation, employee satisfaction and development, training, productivity and performance that contribute to the performance appraisal system.

The recommendations come from practical analyzes to determine the differences between employees and managers participating in the key performance roles of the organization. In this case, adjustments are needed to get the best advantage of supporting the performance appraisal system. If there is also a general level of satisfaction with senior management, but also arise the bias which need to alignment from the perspectives of managers and employees. However, introduce formal reporting mechanisms to eliminate biases and improve the inflow of benefits to enhance the advantages from performance appraisal system.

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